

كتاب قصيدة المرثية (Kitab Qasidat al-Marsiyyah).

also known as "The book of an elegy poem"

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Entry tags: Uthmaniyyah, Religious Group, Islamic Theology, Abrahamic, Text, Islam, Islam in Africa, Islamic Traditions, Islamic Revival

The book was written by Nana Asma'u, the daughter of Sheikh Uthman ibn Fodio of the ancient Sokoto Caliphate of Nigeria, in commemoration of her deceased brother (Muhammad Bello) whom ibn Fodio appointed to rule the eastern part of the caliphate (1817-1837). She described most of his kind traits as worthy of emulation to the entire people of the caliphate and those in need of eternal success in the hereafter and finally concluded with stanzas of supplication to request the forgiveness of his shortcomings and make paradise his eternal abode.

Date Range: 1793 CE - 1864 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Fodio, A. (1937). Kitab qasi-datul marsi-yah.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP535-1-4-2-36>

– Source 1 Description: British Library

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <http://fm6oa.org/revue/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/ibtissam-ahmed-5.pdf>

– Source 1 Description: Ahmed I. (2022). The Life and Contributions of Nana Asmau. Mujallatul Ulama'il Afariqah.

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.pressreader.com/nigeria/daily-trust-saturday/20170603/282265255393773>

– Source 1 Description: Nana Asma'u

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: A handwritten copy of the book.

Inked

– with Ink

Notes: The poem was written with locally made black ink.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: The text was copied on white paper.

Specify type of paper

– Specify: white paper

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Notes: The material was a modified copy of the emir of Kano.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Notes: The introductory statement was an indication of an additional comment to identify the writer of the poem.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The uploaded copy of the emir of Kano served as an indication of its storage for usage purposes, especially at homes and archives or libraries.

↳ Tomb

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in any tomb.

↳ Cemetery

– No

Notes: The book was not kept in the cemetery.

↳ Temple

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in any temple.

↳ Shrine

– No

Notes: The text has no relation to a shrine, hence was not kept there.

↳ Altar

– No

Notes: The book was not placed on altar.

↳ Devotional marker

– No

Notes: The text was not stored at any devotional marker.

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Notes: The text was not stored at the cenotaph.

↳ Church

– No

Notes: The text belongs to the Islamic religion and hence has no relation to the church.

↳ Mosque

– No

Notes: It was not kept in mosques.

↳ Synagogue

– No

Notes: The book was not kept in the synagogue.

↳ Triumphal Arch

– I don't know

Notes: The text was not stored in the triumphal arch.

↳ Monument

– No

Notes: The text was not reserved in any place of commemoration.

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

Notes: The book was not stored in the location of the mass gathering.

↳ Cave(s)

– No

Notes: The text was not stored in the caves.

↳ Hilltops

– I don't know

Notes: The book was not kept at a hilltop.

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– I don't know

Notes: The text was not stored in any place having a natural sanctuary.

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

Notes: The text was not kept at any boundary line.

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Notes: Many people copied the text for their personal uses at home.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Some copies of the text were kept at libraries and archives for reservation purposes and the use of the people.

↳ Specify

– Specify: Some copies were kept in some non-formal educational institutions.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: It was only kept with a level on the front page of the text, as indicated by the uploaded cover page.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: No iconic image was made to identify the text.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: The text was sponsored by the caliphate indirectly, as was done in Moan to the death of the caliph Muhammad Bello, as such; it attracted the attention of the caliphate officials.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– No

Notes: They expect a reward from Allah for the dissemination of Knowledge.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– I don't know

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

Notes: The leadership of the caliphate was based on religious and educational levels.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the political officials are involved in the textual production of the text.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: Political officials stand the roles of religious duties in some instances.

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Notes: The text highlighted some moral traits that are encouraged by Islam.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

Notes: Legal codes of the caliphate are derived from the Qur'an and Hadith, not the book.

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

Notes: No monetary treatment was attached to the production of the text.

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Some partake in the production of the text voluntarily.

↳ Present full-time?

– No

Notes: is voluntarily

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

Notes: They did copied the book in addition to their other personal activities.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

Notes: Religious specialty is by education alone.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

Notes: Religious specialty is by piety and knowledge alone.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

Notes: Religious specialty is not by class, but open to anybody

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– Yes

Notes: They always remain in place for the necessary transformation of the caliphate.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

Notes: Specialists are stratified in the hierarchy of judges, Imams, scholars, etc.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– No

Notes: No segregation by hierarchy.

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Every class of specialist has its distinct position to stand within the palace of the caliphate.

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Judges are said to receive special training in the caliphate.

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: The caliphate established an educational ministry and was entrusted to manage religious institutions.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Notes: The text was written in the Arabic language, the only language of Islamic religious services in the caliphate

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– I don't know

Notes: The endogenous language of the text was Fulfulde.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: The language of the text was exogenous to the group, as was brought to the caliphate from Arabia.

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– Yes

Notes: But not necessarily.

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Prophet

Notes: The language of the text was made sacred by the prophet (SAW).

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

Notes: Teaching the content of the text was purely religious.

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: They used Fulani and Hausa language to support the study of the text.

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Stanzas of the text was chanted to aid easy memorization.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 20000000

Notes: The caliphate covered a wide range of West Africa that cut across Nigeria, Niger, Cameroon, Chad, and Ganah, whose estimated population extends to about 20,000000.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 15000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 10000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 20000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Birth rate, Death rate, Migration and war

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 150000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 10000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 150000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Birth rate, Migration and slavery

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text did not clearly state the reward of proselytizing.

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: Is not by mandate

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– I don't know

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Some versions of the book were copied by different authors, with little comments on the meaning of some technical terms, while; others are translations into other languages to aid a better understanding of the text.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Both versions are proper, as none made any change that could divert its original meaning.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

Notes: The difference could only exist in the additional comments that might add up to the number of pages of the original book.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: It was a single book having only five pages.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text started with an invocation in Allah's Name to seek forgiveness for her deceased brother

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or

aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?
– Generally positive

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?
– Specify: positive

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?
– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?
– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?
– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?
– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?
– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: It is real and not temporal

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: The language in the afterlife shall be Arabic, as stated by the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) in his tradition.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

↳ Personal effects?

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– No

↳ Other grave goods?

– Yes

Notes: Nothing is allowed to be accompanied in the grave apart from the shroud.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

–Specify: No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: He unquestionable in His decision

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: He is self-sufficient

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: His knowledge has no restriction to some affairs

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: His knowledge extends to all regions

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes
- ↳ Can reward
– Yes
- ↳ Can punish
– Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

–Specify: Has control over everything

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: Communicate through revelation

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: To His Messengers

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: Through Messengers alone

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– No

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Specify: creatures

Notes: The pointed human spirit knows other creatures living with man, such as animals and their likes.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - No
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Yes
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
 - ↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The text did not indicated that.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: movement

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Notes: The field does not know.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Angels are assigned to record the deeds of human beings.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

Notes: Angels record murder against the person to have committed it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: They do not have a desire for sex.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: They record it against the person, as God prohibits it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: Angels record oath breached against the person, based on the directives of God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– I don't know

Notes: Supernatural monitors cared about laziness, especially that might lead to religious weakness in society based on the directives of God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

Notes: Supernatural monitors do not care about sorcery.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitors record it against the person to have disrespect elders unjustly.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– I don't know

Notes: Supernatural monitors record gossip against a person on the directives of the God to have prohibited it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitors record it against the person to have committed a property crime on the directives of God having control over all.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitors record rewards to the proper ritual observer on the directives of God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: Supernatural care about others, especially those assigned to him on monitorship.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Especially angels

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: Breaching His laws is the leading cause of punishment

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

- ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
 - No
- ↳ Other form of punishment
 - Specify: Painful torment punishment
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Other?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The text is silent on messianism, only that other texts; in the community affirmed it concerning Fortold Imam Mahadi.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The request of forgiveness to the deceased indicated the reality of the eschaton.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: Eschaton will be in the afterlife.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

Notes: The time was not specified.

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

Notes: The time is unspecified in the future.

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Field doesn't know

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Actually, the time is not known to any except God.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

Notes: They don't have the power to terminate the world.

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: The text affirmed the divine judgment.

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

Notes: The text kept silent on the restoration of the world.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

Notes: In the grave

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

Notes: Power and control belong to Allah alone.

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

Notes: Eternal life shall be on the reward or punishment judged on the deeds of humans.

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: Paradise, Hellfire etc.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Notes: Except God alone.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text shortlisted some social norms, especially when identifying the moral conduct of the late caliph

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts
– No

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities
– No

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)
– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)
– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
– Yes
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– I don't know

Notes: The text prohibited suicide.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: Charity to other poor individuals.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 2

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– Number of participants: 80

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– Hours: 2

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– Yes

↳ Food taboos?

– No

↳ Hair?

– Yes

↳ Dress?

– Yes

↳ Ornaments?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: cleanliness

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: Mandatory for some to have a specified amount of Zakat

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– No

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Is to be given to some specified individuals

Notes: These specified individuals are; poor, orphans, etc.

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– No

Notes: Volunteer staff

↳ Other?

–Specify: care of the place

Notes: By regular maintenance and tiding the place from dirty.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: The society to have produced the text is best described as Sokoto Caliphate, established by Sheikh Uthman ibn Fodio.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No societal element of destruction is associated with the text

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– Yes

Notes: Zakat (Obligatory charity) and Sadaqah (voluntary charity) were institutionalized as famine relief.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: Zakat (obligatory charity) and Sadaqah (voluntary charity) are among the poverty relief mechanisms institutionalized by the text.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– Yes

Notes: The text pointed to elderly care when identifying the best qualities of the deceased person.

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text encouraged working hard to earn means of livelihood from which others could be supported financially.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: It is being taught at various schools within the caliphate.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: It guided an educational institution responsible for teaching the text.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Education is for all

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: A reward is only reserved in the hereafter.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: The text identified better qualities of leadership that bureaucrats are expected to rule on for the betterment of society.

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: The text pointed to trustworthiness while interacting with public works.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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